

The Hydrogen atom in quantised space

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In theoretical physics the origin of the smallest phenomena – the structure of atoms – is not well known. Although the Standard model of particle physics describes the derived structure of high energy particles that emerge from experiments with particle colliders. In this paper I try to derive the general structure of the Hydrogen atom with the help of the model of quantised space.

Introduction

The model of quantised space predicts that the quantisation of the volume of the universe shows a metric of units with a size of about $0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m. The continuous topological changes of the units of the spatial structure under invariant volume have a frequency of about $5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ Hz. In other words, it is not realistic to speculate that we can simulate the original structure and non-local nature of physical reality at the smallest scale size. Not at least because quantised space is the rest frame of the universe.

But may be it is possible to construct a general picture of what is going on at the atomic scale size of phenomenological reality with the help of what we know in physics. To reduce the amount of text I don't describe the model of quantised space. It can be find in the references.^{[1][2][3]}

References:

1. S.E. Grimm (2024); “The box without walls”
<https://zenodo.org/record/14540104>
2. S.E. Grimm (2020); “On the construction of the properties of discrete space”
<https://zenodo.org/record/3909268>
3. S.E. Grimm (2024); “On the geometrical structure of quantised space”
<https://zenodo.org/record/14556269>

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Non-locality

There are 2 types of non-locality. A topological non-locality and a vector non-locality. The topological non-locality is created by the synchronisation of the quantised deformation of the units of quantised space under influence of the

internal spherical shape forming mechanism of every unit. We don't observe the non-locality of the deforming units (the universal electric field) as a distinct property. We interpret this type of non-locality as the “cause and effect” between the phenomena.

Vector non-locality is more difficult to observe because it questions cause and effect. It acts instantaneously and the position of the reach of a vector in vacuum space is undetermined for the observer. We can only observe its effect on the behaviour of the phenomena. It results in non-local influences like [quantum entanglement](#). The general conclusion is that phenomena like atoms don't exist by themselves. Atoms are part of phenomenological reality and atoms emerge from the mutual influences between the units of quantised space, the rest frame of the universe. In line with [Parmenides](#)' concept of reality.

If we put atoms in a closed vessel and we start subtracting nearly all the energy from the volume inside the vessel the boundaries of the enclosed atoms slowly start to merge ([Bose-Einstein condensate](#); see [animation](#)). It proves that atoms represent a dynamical equilibrium. The direct relation between the amount of the average energy density in vacuum space and the properties of an atom questions the mechanism of the relation. Because if there is a large supply of energy – like the turbulent energy conditions in a star – atoms cannot sustain their spatial configuration and disintegrate into solitary particles. It shows that the emergence of atoms in the universe is determined by the geometrical conditions in vacuum space.

Therefore vacuum space is not the manifestation of a neutral background everywhere in the universe. The universe evolves and therefore the geometrical conditions in vacuum space will change too.

Decreased scalars

Concentrations of energy are created by the internal spherical shape forming mechanism of every unit of quantised space. We cannot know “the stuff” a unit is build of so for us the internal spherical shape forming mechanism of the unit is the nature of the unit. It means that every unit is constantly pushing against the units around to get a more

symmetrical (= spherical) shape. Above a certain number of units that are involved in the concentration of topological deformation the scalar of the unit in the centre of the concentration is forced to decrease its radius. The decreased radius disrupts the vector network that is mediated by the points of contact between the scalars (the flat Higgs field – [Kepler’s conjecture](#) – see figure 1).

figure 1

Figure 2 shows in a *schematic* way (cross-section) the simplified structure of the units of quantised space (cubes). In the centre we find units with a high amount of topological deformation (a particle) and inside the particle there is a unit with a decreased scalar (red). The scalars of the adjacent units (black) of the unit in the centre have only 11 vectors because these units have no point of contact with the decreased scalar in the centre of the particle (red).

figure 2

The 12 missing vectors are equal to the magnitude of 1 scalar in vacuum space (flat Higgs field). The consequence is the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around (red arrows) and each of these vectors point towards the decreased scalar. Note that the drawn vectors (red) are *result-*

ant vectors because every scalar of a unit of quantised space that is part of vacuum space at that moment (flat Higgs field) has always 12 vectors (12 points of contact).

The motion of a local concentration of energy – for example a proton – is the propagation of its surplus amount of topological deformation (energy) in relation to the average topological deformation within the structure of quantised space. But the pass on of the proton within the structure of quantised space is also the pass on of the vectorisation of the Higgs field by the decreased scalar (red arrows) and the topological deformation of the units around.^[4]

The term “*vectorisation of the Higgs field by the decreased scalar*” isn’t a clear description of the vectors (red) in figure 2. These vectors are described in Newtonian gravity. Nevertheless, these vectors don’t represent an attracting force between matter objects. The “attracting force” is the result of vector shielding.^[5] That is why the force of gravity in vacuum space at the macroscopic scale size is so extremely small in relation to the electromagnetic force.

References:

4. S.E. Grimm (2024); “*On resultant motion in discrete space*” <https://zenodo.org/records/11193931>
5. S.E. Grimm (2025); “*Entwined forces in quantised space*” <https://zenodo.org/records/17716188>

Energy concentration

Figure 3 shows a particle M and inside a unit with a decreased scalar. It means that before the particle emerged from vacuum space around, a huge amount of units have transferred topological deformation (energy) towards the centre. The amount of units (volume in vacuum space) that was needed to decrease the scalar is represented by the (imaginary) red dotted circle A. But it is reasonable to assume that the total amount of energy that is concentrated is much larger – black dotted circle B – because protons don’t decay, therefore a threshold has been passed.

figure 3

If this is correct, the topological deformation of the unit with the decreased scalar in the centre of the particle is higher than the deformation that is equal to the threshold that is needed to decrease a scalar. The total magnitude of the gravitational vectors that represent the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around the particle – the red arrows in figure 2 – is equal to the threshold. The units within volume B minus A have also decreased their amount of topological deformation and therefore also the corresponding magnitude of their vectors within the magnetic field. At the moment the scalar in the centre starts to decrease its radius, the gravitational vectors emerge. In other words, the continuation of the concentration of energy occurs while the vectorisation around the particle exists. So it is reasonable to expect that these missing vectors of the transferred energy of volume B minus A are in the centre of the concentration. The emerging particle itself and maybe also in the units close to the boundary of the particle (the grey rasterised concentric shells in figure 1).

The propagation of a rest mass carrying particle within the structure of quantised space creates its own dipole.^[6] Figure 4 shows the forced dipole. The white arrow shows the direction of the propagation and the forced “stress” of the units around (red and blue). The black arrows represent the vectors of the magnetic field that are created because of the forced deformation of the shape of the units by the propagating particle. There is a neutral zone too, perpendicular to the direction of the motion of the particle.

figure 4

The neutral zone isn't without vectors of the magnetic field but these vectors are parallel in relation to the direction of the propagation of the particle. Thus there is no push forward or backward in relation to the propagation of the particle in figure 4.

References:

- S.E. Grimm (2025); “The dipole in quantised space” <https://zenodo.org/record/14630170>

The Hydrogen atom

The geometrical properties of a neutron are a bit mysterious because we cannot observe a neutron inside an atomic nucleus. At the moment a free neutron transforms into a proton, vacuum space around the proton is vectorised because of the decreased scalar (figure 2) and the nucleus creates its dipole too (figure 4). If I combine both figures I get figure 5. It shows in a schematic way a “snapshot” of the proton and the configuration of vacuum space around.

figure 5

The image shows that the neutral zone of the dipole is permeated by the dominant vectors that are created by the decreased scalar of the proton (red arrows). The direction of the propagation of the proton is the same as the direction in figure 4. Thus the spiral propagation of the topological deformation of the units around the proton is perpendicular to the direction of the propagation of the proton.

Somehow the electron emerges from the conditions that are expressed in the schematic figure 5. It is reasonable to assume that the orbital plane of the electron is equal to the neutral zone in figure 5 and it will have the direction of the propagating of the helical topological deformation because the circular neutral zone is actually a helix.

There exists variance of properties in the neutral zone because the further away from the proton the less influence on the deformation of the units by the vectors, generated by the decreased scalar (red arrows in figure 2). In other words, the further away from the proton in the neutral

zone, the more likely the emergence of a concentration of energy we have termed “electron”.

If the velocity of the propagation of the Hydrogen atom in relation to the rest frame decreases, the “push” of the nucleus in relation to vacuum space around (figure 4) will not decrease, neither the gravitational vectors of the decreased scalar (figure 2). So maybe we can consider that figure 5 shows the cross section of a configuration that creates the boundary of a Hydrogen atom (^1H) in relation to the conditions of vacuum space around the boundary of the atom.

If the idea of a surplus of energy at the edge of the neutral zone is true, it is reasonable to imagine a ring (actually a helix) of increased topological deformation around the nucleus. Because the vectors (red arrows) that are generated by the decreased scalar will push an amount of topological deformation from vacuum space towards the nucleus. See figure 6.

figure 6

If I imagine the propagation of a proton in vacuum space, the electron as an imaginary particle accompanies the proton in a atomic orbital. The atomic orbital is actually a helix and the distance between the proton and the electron is fixed if there is no energy supply. Figure 8 shows the situation.

Now the question arises if the properties of the proton during the propagation in vacuum space are constant. Because the topological deformation of the unit of the decreased scalar in the centre of the proton must be passed on to an adjacent unit. So I assume that it is possible that the magnitude of the vectors (red arrows in figure 2) is interrupted. It is for sure that the interruption will influence the properties of the electron. No matter if the electron is a noticeable particle or a standing wave. The latter is predicted in quantum mechanics.

figure 7

If the magnitude of the vectors of a decreased scalar is interrupted because of the pass on of the proton from a unit to an adjacent unit, the distance between proton and electron (distance a in figure 7) will periodically change. If this is correct, the velocity of the proton in relation to the structure of quantised space will determine the wave properties of the electron in its atomic orbital. But that is not what we observe.

Wave phenomena

The linear velocity of the energy of an electromagnetic wave is the speed of light (c) and this constant velocity is the result of the internal spherical shape forming mechanism of every unit of quantised space. The emergence of the wave pattern of an electromagnetic wave (E and B in figure 8) reflects the “push” of the incoming quantum of energy and the resulting “push back” from the units around.

figure 8

In other words, if topological deformation from vacuum space around the boundary of the Hydrogen atom is pushed towards the nucleus by the vectors of the decreased scalar, there will be a push back from the units inside the boundary of the Hydrogen atom. The result is an “electron wave” perpendicular to the linear propagation of the Hydrogen atom in vacuum space. The amount of supplied energy from vacuum space around the boundary of the Hydrogen

atom will be the mass of the electron. The consequence of the mass of the hypothetical “electron ring” (see figure 6) is that the electron mass has a spin.

figure 9

Because an increase of topological deformation results in a decrease of the velocity of propagation in vacuum space. Figure 9 shows the process of energy transfer during the concentration of topological deformation (mass) in vacuum space. The process is comparable with the concentration of clouds of dust and molecules at the cosmic scale size that results in the creation of a protostar and the evolution of its surrounding disk into a planetary system. Figure 10 shows the drawing (?) of a young star with a disk of dust, etc. It underlines that our universe shows itself as a self-generating fractal. So it is reasonable to speculate that the “electron-ring” around the proton – see figure 6 – will evolve into a local energy concentration that shows spin.

figure 10

At the end of the 20th century scientists at the Philips Laboratory in the Netherlands^[7] were able to measure the cross-section of electromagnetic waves. It showed that the size of the cross-section of the electromagnetic wave is $\frac{1}{2}$ its wave length (figure 11). The discovered ratio is intriguing because it shows not only a fixed relation but also the geometry of quantised space. Because the influence of the “incoming” quantum on vacuum space around and *visa versa* show the same speed of light.

figure 11

The ratio between wave length and the wave cross-section tells us something about the constant propagation of the topological deformation of amplitudes within the structure of the universal electric field. First of all it is the confirmation of the constant speed of light in relation to the constant of length (ℓ_c). Second it shows that a local amount of concentrated energy cannot keep up its local surplus of energy in relation to the energy of the other units around in vacuum space.

If we translate the derived “picture” into a local surplus of energy that has spin it is clear that the local surplus of energy must have a wave form too. Not exactly the wave form of an electromagnetic wave, but a waveform that is a sequence of a repetitive concentration and de-concentration of local energy. The consequence is that the electron and its supposed “carrier” waveform cannot be two individual phenomena.

A Helium atom (${}^4\text{He}$) has 2 electrons and the nucleus of the atom is a composition of 2 protons and 2 neutrons. Electrons have a negative electric charge ($-e$) and protons have a positive electric charge ($+e$). The electric charge of an anti-proton is equal to the electric charge of an electron.

So in theory it is possible to replace one of the 2 electrons of the ${}^4\text{He}$ atom with an anti-proton ([anti-protonic Helium](#)). A couple of years ago experiments showed that anti-protonic Helium exists,^[8] although the anti-protonic Helium atom is not stable. The anti-proton starts circling towards the nucleus and the end-result is annihilation. However, the anti-proton within the boundary of the Helium atom is not a standing wave. Therefore we can speculate about the existence of an electron as a particle in the atomic orbital. The latter shows some similarities with the [atomic model of Niels Bohr](#). Although Bohr’s model was mainly derived with the help of the radiation and absorption data.

References:

7. E. Montie, E. Cosman, G. 't Hooft, et al. (1991); “*Observation of the optical analogue of quantized conductance of a point contact*”.
Nature 350, 594–595 (1991)
<https://doi.org/10.1038/350594a0>
8. Sótér, A., Aghai-Khozani, H., Barna, D. et al. 2022); “*High-resolution laser resonances of antiprotonic helium in superfluid 4He.*”
Nature 603, 411–415 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04440-7>

The atomic orbital

The waveform of an electromagnetic wave manifests itself in vacuum space (figure 8 and 11). It shows that the quantum of energy represents a local disturbance of a symmetrical equilibrium. A local concentration of energy – like an electron – doesn’t represent the same geometrical symmetry. But it is obvious that during the propagation of an electron the particle will experience the universal sequence of push/push-back that is caused by the internal spherical shape forming mechanism of the involved units.

If we imagine a Hydrogen atom and the electron-wave in its atomic orbital – like figure 7 – the question arises if the frequency of the waveform exists “independently” from the properties of the nucleus. Because figure 11 suggests a fixed relation that rules the distribution of free energy in vacuum space. The relation is expressed in the Planck-Einstein relation:

$$E = h \nu = h \frac{c}{\lambda} \quad \rightarrow \quad h \frac{c}{n \ell_c}$$

The wave length (λ) is replaced by a multiple of the constant of length ($\ell_c \approx 0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m) to express the direct relation between the structure of quantised space and phenomenological reality. The consequence is that the pass on of 1 quantum of energy from 1 side of a unit to the opposite side has a duration of $t_q \approx 5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ second. The velocity of light (c) is a universal constant thus t_q is the universal constant of quantum time ($\ell_c = c \times t_q$).

In figure 8 we see the push to distribute the quantum of energy (fixed amount of topological deformation) over more units ($0 \rightarrow 1$), the push-back of the units to concentrate the previous deformation ($1 \rightarrow 2$), the prolonged push-back that result in distribution again ($2 \rightarrow 3$) and next the push to concentrate the deformation ($3 \rightarrow 4$). The whole sequence creates the wave length. The energy of the electromagnetic

wave is directly related to its frequency (ν) and figure 11 shows that the distribution of energy in vacuum space represents fixed relations. In line with $\ell_c = c \times t_q$.

The conclusion is that the waveform of an electron-wave cannot be separated from the conditions of the electron within (and outside) the structure of the Hydrogen atom. So what are these conditions?

Figure 12 shows in a schematic way the units of quantised space (small cubes). In the centre a proton thus the flat Higgs field around the proton is vectorised (red arrows). The consequence is that the dominant deformation of the units around the proton is in the direction towards the proton. The viewpoint in figure 12 is the cross-section of the neutral zone in figure 4 and the proton moves perpendicular to the cross-section. The topological deformation of all the units in quantised space is synchronised thus adjacent units cannot deform in opposite directions.

figure 12

The blue concentric circles represent the *resultant* direction of deformation of the units (the small cubes). In other words, the situation is nearly comparable with figure 9 although in figure 9 the flat Higgs field isn’t vectorised. The propagation of the deformation in vacuum space around the particle – the neutral zone – isn’t circular but helical (see figure 7). The velocity of the *resultant* deformation – the concentric circles in figure 12 – is the velocity of the proton. In other words, for the co-moving observer it is like the deformation of the units orbits the proton.^[4]

The velocity of the propagation of deformation in vacuum space around the proton is the resultant velocity ($v_r < c$). But every resultant velocity corresponds with the linear ve-

locity of an amount of concentrated energy. We will find the atomic orbital of the electron at a distant where the velocity of the mass of the electron corresponds with the resultant velocity of the deformation of the units. For example the grey rasterised orbit in figure 12.

The mass of an electron is the 1836th part of the mass of the proton and its (classic) radius is about $1,8 \times 10^{-15}$ m. The (classic) size of the electron doesn't exclude its existence within in the neutral zone of the dipole of the proton. If this is correct the electron of a Hydrogen atom must have particle properties in its atomic orbital. Because the electron has a surplus of concentrated energy, it has spin and a dipole (because of this surplus of energy, see figure 9) and it has a fixed position in relation to the direction of the motion of the proton (co-moving like a planet in its orbit around a star). However, the electron has no decreased scalar inside thus its proportions (size and shape) are not almost fixed and will show variance.

figure 13

The image above is actually figure 7 but now I use the image for the supposed electron waveform. From left to right “all” the positions of the proton during its propagation in vacuum space. I have drawn a couple of neutral zones too (grey) and the influence of the gravitational vectors of the flat Higgs field (red arrows). Where the trajectory of the electron (blue line) crosses a drawn neutral zone, I have drawn an electron in the right position. In other words, it is like the electron exists at the front of an “incoming” energy density from vacuum space around (the edge is at the 2 dotted horizontal blue lines).

How do we measure the wave form of an electron in its atomic orbital? Not at the inside of the Hydrogen atom. So I cannot know for certain that the wave length of the electron in the ground state of the Hydrogen atom is the wave length of the electron or that the measured wave length is the variable “push” of the energy of vacuum

space within the neutral zone. Because the helical moving electron will create a local waveform of the energy of vacuum space within the neutral zone. Figure 14 explains in a schematic way the idea.

figure 14

The electron is co-moving (v_c) with the proton (v). Energy in vacuum space is pushed by the gravitational vectors (red arrows) in the neutral zone towards the proton. Thus if I measure the electromagnetic field in A (vacuum space) the outcome is an electromagnetic wave that is synchronised with the helical motion of the electron.

The image in figure 14 raises a question about the origin of the electric charge. Not at least because experiments have showed that the electric charge is **relativistic invariant**. It means that the electric charge of a particle ($e+$, $e-$) doesn't change if its velocity increases or decreases. Comparable with the total sum of the magnitudes of the gravitational vectors of a decreased scalar that are invariant to the linear velocity of the proton.

Conclusion

The attempt to describe known properties of the constituents of the Hydrogen atom with the help of the model of quantised space shows a slightly different “picture” of what is going on at the smallest scale size. More in line with the atomic model of Bohr. Although there are other known facts about the different states of the Hydrogen atom that are still confusing. That means that the used concepts – in relation to the Hydrogen atom – show too much focus on locality.